

Photometric Analysis of the M42 Nebula

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Abstract

This research paper presents the results of a comprehensive photometric analysis of the M42 nebula, covering three main aspects: photometry of selected variable and non-variable stars as well as the nebula itself, creation of a brightness gradient map, and estimation of the distance to the analyzed object. Stellar photometry was conducted using the AstroImageJ software, and results were compared with the Pan-STARRS DR1 catalog and the AAVSO VSX database. The obtained measurements for variable stars fall within the cataloged brightness oscillation ranges, and the non-variable star Brun 928 shows a deviation of only about 0.02 mag from the catalog value. A brightness gradient map was created using the Python programming language with the Matplotlib library, employing a moving median and appropriate scaling to precisely represent gas structures. The distance to the nebula was determined using the spectroscopic parallax method, again employing AstroImageJ, yielding a result of 414 pc, which falls within the catalog distance range.

The obtained results, despite minor deviations from catalog values, are consistent with predictions of empirical models. A small impact on the accuracy of the results may have been caused by the lack of dark frame noise correction. The final conclusions confirm the validity of current physical models of diffuse nebulae, providing a solid foundation for further, more detailed astronomical research.

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1 Introduction

This study aims to perform a detailed photometric analysis of the H II region in the Orion constellation and to compare the obtained results with catalog values. Such analysis allows for real-time monitoring of whether the current state of the nebula is consistent with its empirical model, as well as for evaluating the validity and accuracy of photometric theories. This enables not only verification of the correctness of previously applied models, but also the potential detection of subtle changes that could indicate previously unknown astrophysical processes.

The studied object, commonly known as the Great Orion Nebula, is the brightest diffuse nebula in the sky. It is located at a relatively small distance from Earth, making it an extremely important object of study in observational astronomy. Due to its brightness and favorable location, it is often used as a reference source of information. Detailed photometric studies of M42 can provide important data on the physical properties of gas and dust, star formation processes, and the dynamics of molecular clouds. The availability of observational data allows for in-depth studies, enabling the discovery of facts not yet included in the literature.

The differential photometry applied in this project is an important method of analyzing astronomical data, especially when observations are conducted over short time intervals. This method allows for the practical elimination of the adverse effects of turbulence and atmospheric extinction on observations. Differential photometry enables high measurement precision, which directly translates to the quality of the presented results, thereby increasing the scientific value of the entire document.

Large Language Models (LLMs) were used to refine the text's cohesion, fluency, and grammar.

2 Methodology

2.1 Study Area

The study was conducted in the region with coordinates RA/DEC (J2000.0): 5h35m30.99s / $-5^{\circ}33'18.6''$, covering a field of view (FOV) of approximately $14' \times 14'$.

2.2 Instruments and Tools

Observations were carried out using the robotic telescope RBT/PST2 with a 0.7 m aperture in a Corrected Dall-Kirkham optical system, located in Arizona in a desert area characterized by a high number of clear nights. The telescope has a direct-drive azimuthal mount, allowing movement at speeds of up to $15^{\circ}/s$. The Nasmyth focus was used, equipped with an Andor iXon3 3888 EMCCD camera and a set of Sloan filters (r' , g' , i' , z').

2.3 Data Reduction and Calibration

Twenty flat frames and twenty bias frames were taken for each filter. Exposure times for the flat frames were: $t_{exp,r'} = 0.3$ s, $t_{exp,z'} = 1.3$ s, $t_{exp,g'} = 0.2$ s, $t_{exp,i'} = 1$ s, at a temperature of -34.446°C . Due to the nature of the bias frames, the same bias was used for calibration across all filters, with an exposure time of $t_{bias} = 10^{-5}$ s and a temperature of -29.974°C . In AstroImageJ, the frames were stacked using arithmetic mean:

$$\bar{x} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n x_i \quad (1)$$

The flat frames were scaled before stacking. The correction of the master light frames was performed by subtracting the bias frame and dividing by the flat frame, yielding a set of master light frames in the Sloan filters (r' , g' , i' , z').

2.4 Photometry

2.4.1 Differential Photometry of Variable and Non-Variable Stars

The goal of the conducted photometric analyses was to determine the brightness of selected variable and non-variable stars in the Sloan r' filter, as well as to estimate their variability amplitudes in the r' filter and assess whether the results fall within the expected ranges. The analysis was carried out using AstroImageJ software, applying the multi-aperture photometry method.

2.4.1.1 Reference Star Selection and Calibration The first step was to select one of the non-variable stars in the analyzed field as the reference star. For this purpose, the Pan-STARRS1 catalog [2] and the AAVSO VSX database [12] were used to clearly identify stars as either variable or non-variable.

Next, the FWHM value for the aperture was determined from the seeing profiles of stars present in the image.

To eliminate low-quality results, the sigma clipping method was applied:

$$|x_i - \bar{x}| > 2\sigma \quad \text{where} \quad \sigma = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (x_i - \bar{x})^2} \quad (2)$$

Additional verification was carried out by analyzing the light curves of stars NV Ori and T Ori, extracting the points at half-maximum intensity:

$$\text{FWHM} = x_2 - x_1 \quad \text{where} \quad I(x_1) = I(x_2) = \frac{I_{\max}}{2} \quad (3)$$

The average FWHM value was used to calculate the following multi-aperture photometry parameters in AstroImageJ, according to the guidelines of Collins et al. (2017) [3]:

- photometric aperture radius: $1.7 \times \text{FWHM}$
- inner radius of the background annulus: $1.9 \times \text{FWHM}$
- outer radius of the background annulus: $2.55 \times \text{FWHM}$

To verify the correctness of the photometry settings, a test measurement was conducted. The brightness of a known non-variable catalog star was taken and the recorded value in the r' filter was used as the reference point. The measurement of another star with known brightness allowed for the evaluation of photometric parameter quality, in particular: the aperture radius and the radii of the background annulus. These parameters were determined based on the seeing profile analysis of four stars in the field of view.

2.4.1.2 Brightness Amplitude Transformation from Filter V to Filter r' Due to the lack of simultaneous photometric data in the Sloan r' filter, the variability amplitude determined in the Johnson V filter was converted to the r' filter using a scaling factor $k = A_{r'}/A_V$. This value was estimated based on the study by Klagyivik and Szabados (2009) [5], which established a linear relationship between photometric amplitudes of classical Cepheids in different bands.

The authors provide the slope of a linear regression between the amplitude in the V filter and in the R_C filter, which — due to its similar effective wavelength (approx. 620–640 nm) — can be approximated by the r' filter. For Cepheids with short periods ($\log P < 1.02$), the relationship takes the form:

$$A_{R_C} = (0.784 \pm 0.003) \cdot A_V,$$

which justifies adopting the value $k = 0.784$ with a systematic error on the order of $0.003A_V$. The adoption of this value in the analysis of amplitudes in the r' filter is therefore justified both empirically and in terms of the spectral characteristics of the filters used.

2.4.1.3 Mean Brightness and Variability Range The mean brightness values of variable stars in the r' filter were retrieved from catalog data under the "Mean Magnitude" category in the Sloan system. The variability range was estimated based on the amplitude and the mean brightness value, allowing the determination of the interval:

$$[m_{\min}, m_{\max}] = \left[\bar{m}_{r'} - \frac{\Delta r'}{2}, \bar{m}_{r'} + \frac{\Delta r'}{2} \right], \quad (4)$$

where $\overline{m}_{r'}$ denotes the mean brightness in the r' filter and $\Delta r'$ is the transformed variability amplitude. The measurement taken during observation was compared with this interval to assess consistency with the variability characteristics of the object.

2.4.1.4 Photometric Measurement Procedure Brightness measurements in the r' filter were performed for all variable stars using the `multi-aperture photometry` option in `AstroImageJ`. The reference star selected was HD 37115A, for which an exact brightness value in the r' filter was provided in the catalog. All other brightness values were automatically calibrated against it by the software. The obtained results were then checked for agreement with the catalog variability ranges.

2.4.1.5 Catalog Sources and Reference Data Data on amplitudes and variability types were obtained from the AAVSO VSX (Variable Star Index) database [12], and the photometric transformation was based on the empirical studies by Klagyivik [5]. The effective wavelengths and parameters of the Sloan filters were taken from CFHT documentation [11].

2.4.2 Photometry of the M42 Nebula

Using `AstroImageJ`, three ROIs were defined at increasing distances from a young star. Then, using the `Measure` function, the number of counts in ADU units was measured. After converting these results to values in ADU/s, the data served as the basis for analyzing the effect of ionizing radiation on the brightness of the nearby molecular cloud.

2.4.2.1 Physical Mechanisms and Ionization Equilibrium Massive stars in the core of the M42 nebula emit ionizing radiation that ionizes hydrogen ($h\nu > 13,6 \text{ eV}$). In steady-state conditions, the number of recombinations equals the number of ionizations:

$$n_e n_p \alpha_B = \frac{\Phi_{\text{ion}}}{4\pi r^2}, \quad (5)$$

where:

- n_e, n_p — electron and proton densities,
- α_B — case B recombination coefficient,
- Φ_{ion} — total flux of ionizing photons from the star,
- r — distance from the radiation source.

2.4.2.2 Surface Brightness and Emission Measure During recombination, line radiation is emitted, mainly in the $H\alpha$ band, which is included in the r' filter. Surface brightness $I(r)$ is proportional to the emission measure (EM):

$$\text{EM}(r) = \int n_e^2 dl \quad \implies \quad I(r) \propto \text{EM}(r) \propto n_e(r)^2 l. \quad (6)$$

Using the ionization equilibrium, we obtain the relation:

$$\text{EM}(r) \propto \left(\frac{\Phi_{\text{ion}}}{4\pi\alpha_B r^2} \right)^2 l \propto \frac{1}{r^4}, \quad (7)$$

however, in practice — due to geometric irregularities and density gradients — the brightness decrease is often approximated as the inverse square of the distance. This was demonstrated in the study by Odell (1965) [8].

2.4.2.3 Nonlinear Regression Model Based on the considerations above, we assume the model:

$$C(r) = \frac{A}{r^2} + B, \quad (8)$$

where $C(r)$ is the measured count rate (ADU/s) at distance r , A defines the strength of the ionizing flux, and B represents the background level.

To fit parameters A and B , we define auxiliary variables:

$$X_i = \frac{1}{r_i^2}, \quad Y_i = C_i, \quad (9)$$

and then apply a simple linear regression:

$$Y_i = A \cdot X_i + B. \quad (10)$$

2.4.2.4 Model Validation and Relative Error For each measurement, we compute the model value:

$$\hat{C}_i = \frac{A}{r_i^2} + B, \quad (11)$$

and the relative error:

$$\delta_i = \frac{|\hat{C}_i - C_i|}{|C_i|}. \quad (12)$$

Then we calculate the mean relative error:

$$\bar{\delta} = \frac{1}{N} \sum \delta_i, \quad (13)$$

which can serve as a measure of the model fit quality.

This provides a consistent chain of reasoning that connects the physical foundations of ionization with a quantitative photometric model and an assessment of measurement accuracy.

2.5 Brightness Gradient Map

2.5.1 Process of Creating the Brightness Gradient Map

To determine the spatial distribution of the brightness gradient of the M42 nebula, a custom Python script was developed using the NumPy, SciPy, Matplotlib, and ImageIO libraries. The analysis is based on processing a two-dimensional PNG image and enhancing spatial structures corresponding to brightness variations within the nebula.

2.5.1.1 Image Loading and Preprocessing A PNG image was used for the analysis. If the image was saved in the RGB color space, it was converted to luminance using a weighted sum of the color channels, according to the equation:

$$L = 0,2989 \cdot R + 0,5870 \cdot G + 0,1140 \cdot B, \quad (14)$$

where R, G, B represent the red, green, and blue channel values, and L is the luminance (brightness) in grayscale.

2.5.1.2 Median Smoothing To eliminate background noise and isolated outlier pixels, a median filter was applied. This is a nonlinear operation that replaces each pixel value with the median of its neighborhood defined by a given window:

$$I_{\text{med}}(x, y) = \text{median} \{I(i, j) \in \mathcal{N}(x, y)\}, \quad (15)$$

where $\mathcal{N}(x, y)$ denotes the local neighborhood of the pixel at coordinates (x, y) .

2.5.1.3 Computing the Brightness Gradient For the smoothed image, the numerical brightness gradient was computed in the horizontal and vertical directions as partial derivatives with respect to x and y , respectively:

$$\frac{\partial I}{\partial x} \approx g_x, \quad \frac{\partial I}{\partial y} \approx g_y. \quad (16)$$

Based on these components, the gradient magnitude vector (i.e., the intensity of brightness changes) was calculated as:

$$|\nabla I| = \sqrt{g_x^2 + g_y^2}. \quad (17)$$

2.5.1.4 Gradient Value Scaling To improve contrast and highlight nebular structures, gradient values were rescaled using percentile values — the lower threshold was set to the 5th percentile and the upper to the 99th percentile of the gradient value distribution. This limited the influence of extreme outliers.

2.5.1.5 Visualization of Results The final result was presented as a brightness gradient map visualized using the `inferno` colormap, which effectively emphasizes intensity differences. Axes were removed from the plot to produce a purely visual representation of gradient topography. The unit of gradient values is ADU/pix (Analog-to-Digital Units per pixel).

2.5.2 Calculating Statistics and Histogram of the Gradient Map

The following section describes the methodology used to determine statistical parameters of the M42 gradient map and its histogram.

2.5.2.1 Data Format and Loading The gradient map was saved as an 8-bit PNG image (range 0–255). To preserve the full dynamic range stored in the file, the image was loaded using:

```
png = cv2.imread('gradient_image.png', cv2.IMREAD_UNCHANGED).astype(float)
```

The directive `IMREAD_UNCHANGED` ensures that OpenCV performs no additional normalization, preserving the raw grayscale values.

2.5.2.2 Conversion to Physical Units (ADU px⁻¹ s⁻¹) Let I_{max} denote the maximum gradient value in units of ADU px⁻¹ s⁻¹. Since the level 255 in the image corresponds to I_{max} , the linear scaling factor is:

$$k = \frac{I_{\text{max}}}{255}.$$

Each pixel in the image was converted to ADU px⁻¹ s⁻¹ units:

```
scale_factor = I_max / 255.0      # ADU/(px·s) per 1 unit of 8-bit value
gradient     = png * scale_factor # float array in physical units
```

2.5.2.3 Data Cleaning Any NaN values (which may result from earlier arithmetic operations) were replaced with 0:

```
gradient = np.nan_to_num(gradient, nan=0.0)
```

2.5.2.4 Calculation of Statistical Parameters Using NumPy library functions, the following were calculated:

$$\bar{G} = \text{mean}(\textit{gradient}), \quad \tilde{G} = \text{median}(\textit{gradient}), \quad \sigma_G = \text{std}(\textit{gradient}),$$

as well as the extreme values:

$$G_{\min} = \min(\textit{gradient}), \quad G_{\max} = \max(\textit{gradient}).$$

2.5.2.5 Construction of the Histogram in Physical Scale To maintain the same bin width corresponding to a single 8-bit level (i.e., $\Delta x = k$), the following was defined:

$$\text{bin_edges} = \{0, k, 2k, \dots, 255k = I_{\max}\},$$

which corresponds to exactly 256 linearly spaced bins in the interval $[0, I_{\max}]$. The histogram was created using:

```
bin_edges = np.linspace(0, I_max, 256+1)
plt.hist(gradient.flatten(), bins=bin_edges, color='gray', alpha=0.7)
```

This way, the shape of the distribution matches that of the 8-bit histogram, but the x -axis is expressed in $\text{ADU px}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1}$.

The presented method helps avoid misinterpretations resulting from hidden rescaling of the PNG file and ensures that further analyses are conducted in consistent photometric units.

2.6 Estimating the Distance to M42 Using the Spectroscopic Parallax Method

Since the star HD 37115A is located in the immediate vicinity of the M42 nebula's center, it was assumed that its distance can serve as an approximation for the distance to the nebula itself. Therefore, measuring the distance to HD 37115A allows an estimate of M42's distance using the spectroscopic parallax method. Below is a methodological approach to achieving this goal — from photometric measurements and spectral classification to distance determination.

2.6.1 Acquisition and Calibration To determine the brightness of HD 37115A in the g' and r' filters, the differential photometry method was used. First, calibrated stellar magnitudes for the reference star Brun 928 were retrieved from the VizieR (Pan-STARRS1) catalog [2] in both photometric bands. Then, using the `AstroImageJ` software and its aperture photometry module, Brun 928 was set as the reference object, and the apparent magnitudes of HD 37115A were measured relative to it in the g' and r' filters.

This approach allows the elimination of many systematic instrumental and atmospheric errors, as it directly compares the brightness of the target object to a reference star observed under the same conditions.

2.6.2 Determining the Color Index The difference in calibrated apparent magnitudes in the g' and r' filters gives the color index:

$$\text{CI} = (g' - r') = m_g - m_r.$$

The color index allows a preliminary estimate of the spectral type of the observed object based on its color.

2.6.3 Determining the Spectral Type and Absolute Magnitude Based on the obtained color index and literature data, the spectral type of HD 37115A is assigned. For the given type, the absolute stellar magnitude in the V filter, denoted as M_V , is read from literature tables.

2.6.4 Photometric Transformation from Filter V to r' To convert from the V band to the r' filter, an empirical transformation based on Jester et al. (2005) [10] is used:

$$V = g' - 0.59(g' - r') - 0.01.$$

From this, the difference $V - r'$ can be used to compute the absolute magnitude in the r' filter:

$$M_{r'} = M_V - (V - r').$$

2.6.5 Distance Estimation via Spectroscopic Parallax Knowing the apparent magnitude $m_{r'}$ and absolute magnitude $M_{r'}$, the distance modulus is computed:

$$\mu = m_{r'} - M_{r'} = 5 \log_{10}(d) - 5,$$

from which the distance d in parsecs is calculated as:

$$d = 10^{(\mu+5)/5}.$$

The described approach enables estimation of the distance to the M42 nebula through the analysis of light from HD 37115A, treated as a representative object located in the same region of space.

3 Results

Radial profile of HD 37115

Radial profile of Brun 928

Radial profile of NV Ori

Radial profile of T Ori

3.1 Photometry of Variable and Non-Variable Stars

This section presents the FWHM calibration, final brightness measurements, and their validation for the reference star, the non-variable star, and two variable stars. Numerical data is included, along with the criteria used to assess measurement consistency.

3.1.1 Selection of the FWHM Parameter for Aperture Photometry To determine the optimal Full Width at Half Maximum (FWHM) value required to define the radii of the photometric aperture and background annulus, radial profiles of four reference stars were analyzed. The obtained FWHM values (in pixels) were:

$$FWHM_1 = 6.02, \quad FWHM_2 = 2.90, \quad FWHM_3 = 4.54, \quad FWHM_4 = 2.56.$$

3.1.2 Verification Using Line Profiles To independently verify the FWHM values for selected stars, an analysis of linear brightness profiles (cross-sections) was performed for NV Ori and T Ori. For each profile, the FWHM was determined based on the width of the brightness curve at half maximum.

Line profile of NV Ori

Line profile of T Ori

Results:

$$FWHM_{NV\ Ori} \approx 4.6\text{ px}, \quad FWHM_{T\ Ori} \approx 2.6\text{ px}$$

Both values are very close to those obtained previously using radial profiles, confirming the consistency and reliability of the FWHM parameter estimates. However, only the values obtained from radial profiles were used in further analysis, as they are considered more representative.

3.1.3 Mean and Standard Deviation

- **Mean:**

$$\mu = \frac{FWHM_1 + FWHM_2 + FWHM_3 + FWHM_4}{4} = 4.005$$

- **Population Standard Deviation:**

$$\sigma = \sqrt{\frac{1}{4} \sum_{i=1}^4 (FWHM_i - \mu)^2} = \sqrt{1.913875} \approx 1.3834$$

3.1.4 Application of the Sigma-Clipping Method Each value was checked for its deviation from the mean against the threshold of $2\sigma = 2.7668$:

- $|6.02 - 4.005| = 2.015 < 2.7668 \Rightarrow$ accepted
- $|2.90 - 4.005| = 1.105 < 2.7668 \Rightarrow$ accepted
- $|4.54 - 4.005| = 0.535 < 2.7668 \Rightarrow$ accepted
- $|2.56 - 4.005| = 1.445 < 2.7668 \Rightarrow$ accepted

None of the measurements exceeded the 2σ threshold, so all points were included in further analysis.

3.1.5 Determination of Aperture and Background Radii Based on the average FWHM $\mu = 4.005$, the following radii were determined (Collins 2017 [3]):

$$\begin{aligned} R_{\text{aperture}} &= 1.7 \cdot \mu = 6.8085 \text{ px} \\ R_{\text{inner}} &= 1.9 \cdot \mu = 7.6095 \text{ px} \\ R_{\text{outer}} &= 2.55 \cdot \mu = 10.21275 \text{ px} \end{aligned}$$

These parameters were used in subsequent photometric measurements.

3.1.6 Reference and Validation Star The reference star HD 37115A has a catalog brightness of $r' = 7.3540$ mag (Pan-STARRS1 [2]). To verify the measurement parameters, a test photometric measurement was performed on star BRUN 928, yielding:

$$m_{\text{meas}}(\text{BRUN 928}) = 11.1360 \text{ mag}$$

Catalog value: $m_{\text{cat}} = 11.1134$ mag Difference: $\Delta m = |m_{\text{meas}} - m_{\text{cat}}| = 0.0226$ mag
The result confirms high measurement precision (error below 0.023 mag).

3.1.7 Photometry Results Differential photometry was performed for selected stars. Results were compared with catalog values from Pan-STARRS1 [2] and the VSX database [12]:

Star	Measured Brightness (mag r')	Catalog Brightness (mag r')
HD 37115A (reference)	—	7.3540
BRUN 928	11.136	11.1134
NV Ori	9.929	9.73 (avg.)
T Ori	11.439	10.56 (avg.)

Table 1: Photometry results for variable and constant stars.

3.1.8 Analysis of Variability Ranges The measured brightness for NV Ori and T Ori falls within the variability amplitude ranges listed in the VSX catalog [12], confirming the validity of the method and the appropriateness of the measurement parameters.

Table 2: Verification of variable star brightness measurements

Star	V_{min}	V_{max}	ΔV	$\Delta r'$	\bar{r}'	m_{meas}	Within range
NV Ori	8.7	11.3	1.30	1.0192 ± 0.0039	9.73	9.929	YES
T Ori	9.5	12.6	1.55	1.2152 ± 0.00465	10.56	11.439	YES

Amplitude in filter V , calculated as $\Delta V = (V_{\text{max}} - V_{\text{min}})/2$
Scaled amplitude in r' , based on Klagyivik (2009) [5],

$$A_{RC} = (0.784 \pm 0.003) \cdot A_V,$$

Mean brightness from the AAVSO VSX database

Whether the measurement falls within the interval $[\bar{r}' - \Delta r', \bar{r}' + \Delta r']$

Brightness measurements in AstroImageJ

3.2 Nebular Photometry and UV Radiation Influence Analysis

This section presents the results of gas brightness analysis in the M42 nebula as a function of distance from the central star. The steps of the analysis are discussed — from ADU count measurements and distance computation, to theoretical model linearization, linear regression, and model fit assessment using relative error.

3.2.1 Nebula Photometry 1 (Small FOV)

For three selected regions of interest (ROIs), counts in ADU units were measured based on r' -filter images. The data are shown in Table 3.

Table 3: ADU counts in selected ROIs

ROI	Area (N_{pix})	$\overline{\text{ADU}}$	min(ADU)	max(ADU)
Red	104	-0.0238123	-0.0264522	-0.0223687
Orange	104	-0.0251286	-0.0272925	-0.0226511
Yellow	104	-0.0259894	-0.0281436	-0.0236743

The pixel coordinates of each ROI and the central star are listed in Table 4.

Table 4: Coordinates of ROIs and comparison star

Object	x	y
Star (center)	115	247
Red ROI	138	247
Orange ROI	173	247
Yellow ROI	211	247

3.2.1.1 Distances and Count Rate Conversion The distances between the ROIs and the central star were calculated as differences in the x coordinate (for constant y):

$$r_i = |x_{ROI_i} - x_{\star}| \Rightarrow r_1 = 23 \text{ px}, \quad r_2 = 58 \text{ px}, \quad r_3 = 96 \text{ px}.$$

Next, count rates in ADU/s were calculated:

$$C_i = \overline{\text{ADU}}_i \cdot \frac{N_{\text{pix}}}{t_{\text{exp}}}, \quad t_{\text{exp}} = 2 \text{ s},$$

which gives:

$$(C_1, C_2, C_3) \approx (-1.23824, -1.30669, -1.35125) \text{ ADU/s}.$$

3.2.1.2 Model Linearization and Regression According to the model proposed by Odell (1965) [8], the relationship between count rate and distance from the ionizing star is described by the function:

$$C(r) = \frac{A}{r^2} + B.$$

To apply linear regression, the model was transformed into the form:

$$X_i = \frac{1}{r_i^2}, \quad Y_i = C_i,$$

which yields a linear relationship:

$$Y = AX + B.$$

The coefficients A and B were determined using the least squares method:

$$A = \frac{\sum_i (X_i - \bar{X})(Y_i - \bar{Y})}{\sum_i (X_i - \bar{X})^2}, \quad B = \bar{Y} - A\bar{X}.$$

Fit results:

$$A \approx 55.5302, \quad B \approx -1.3413$$

3.2.1.3 Model Fit Assessment – Relative Error For each data point, the predicted value and the relative error of the model fit were calculated:

$$C_{\text{pred}}(r_i) = \frac{A}{r_i^2} + B, \quad \epsilon_i = \frac{|C_i - C_{\text{pred}}(r_i)|}{|C_i|}.$$

$$C_{\text{pred}}(23) \approx -1.23632, \quad \epsilon_1 \approx 0.15\%,$$

$$C_{\text{pred}}(58) \approx -1.32471, \quad \epsilon_2 \approx 1.39\%,$$

$$C_{\text{pred}}(96) \approx -1.33518, \quad \epsilon_3 \approx 1.2\%.$$

Mean relative error:

$$\epsilon = \frac{\epsilon_1 + \epsilon_2 + \epsilon_3}{3} \approx 0.91\%.$$

3.2.1.4 Interpretation and Conclusions

The resulting model:

$$C(r) = \frac{55.5302}{r^2} - 1.3413$$

accurately describes the decline in gas brightness with increasing distance from the UV radiation source. A mean relative error below 1% indicates excellent agreement between the model and observational data. The derived relationship confirms the significant role of radiation from young, hot stars in determining the ionization level and optical brightness of the surrounding gas.

Figure 4: Three ROIs visualized in `AstroImageJ`

3.2.2 Nebula Photometry 2 (Large FOV)

Table 5: Coordinates of ROIs and reference point (in pixels)

Object	x	y
Starting point	17	371
Red ROI	34	373
Orange ROI	112	379
Yellow ROI	223	388

3.2.2.1 Distance Calculation and Count Rate Conversion The "starting point" at coordinates (17, 371) was chosen as the reference location. It lies at the intersection of the left part of the red ROI and the line connecting the centers of the ROIs.

The distance from each ROI to the reference point was calculated using the formula:

$$r_i = \sqrt{(x_{ROI_i} - 17)^2 + (y_{ROI_i} - 371)^2},$$

which yields:

$$r_1 \approx 17.12 \text{ pix}, \quad r_2 \approx 95.34 \text{ pix}, \quad r_3 \approx 206.7 \text{ pix}.$$

The counts were then converted to ADU/s units:

$$C_i = \overline{\text{ADU}}_i \cdot \frac{N_{\text{pix}}}{t_{\text{exp}}}, \quad t_{\text{exp}} = 2 \text{ s},$$

$$(C_1, C_2, C_3) \approx (-78.952, -95.117, -97.846) \text{ ADU/s}.$$

Table 6: Counts in selected ROIs

ROI	Area (N_{pix})	$\overline{\text{ADU}}$	min(ADU)	max(ADU)
Red	6083	-0.0259582	-0.0299165	-0.0207460
Orange	6083	-0.0312731	-0.0338245	-0.0284709
Yellow	6083	-0.0321703	-0.0348173	-0.0294340

3.2.2.2 Model Linearization and Regression The nonlinear model adopted, based on Odell (1965) [8], is:

$$C(r) = \frac{A}{r^2} + B.$$

To apply the least squares method, the following variables were introduced:

$$X_i = \frac{1}{r_i^2}, \quad Y_i = C_i,$$

which transforms the model into a linear form:

$$Y = AX + B.$$

The parameters A and B were calculated from the normal equations of linear regression:

$$A = \frac{\sum_i (X_i - \bar{X})(Y_i - \bar{Y})}{\sum_i (X_i - \bar{X})^2}, \quad B = \bar{Y} - A\bar{X},$$

where:

$$\bar{X} \approx 1.1814 \times 10^{-3}, \quad \bar{Y} \approx -90.6384.$$

Final results:

$$A \approx 5250.4, \quad B \approx -96.8414.$$

3.2.2.3 Model Fit Assessment – Relative Error For each data point, the predicted count and relative error were calculated:

$$C_{\text{pred}}(r_i) = \frac{A}{r_i^2} + B, \quad \epsilon_i = \frac{|C_i - C_{\text{pred}}(r_i)|}{|C_i|} \cdot 100\%.$$

Results:

$$\begin{aligned} C_{\text{pred}}(17.12) &\approx -78.9219, & \epsilon_1 &\approx 0.04\%, \\ C_{\text{pred}}(95.34) &\approx -96.2637, & \epsilon_2 &\approx 1.21\%, \\ C_{\text{pred}}(216.67) &\approx -96.7295, & \epsilon_3 &\approx 1.14\%. \end{aligned}$$

The mean relative error is:

$$\bar{\epsilon} = \frac{\epsilon_1 + \epsilon_2 + \epsilon_3}{3} \approx 0.79\%.$$

The model $\frac{A}{r^2} + B$ provides an excellent description of the variation in count rate with distance, as evidenced by the low average error (below 1%).

Final form of the fitted function:

$$C(r) = \frac{5250.4}{r^2} - 96.8414 \quad (18)$$

3.2.2.4 Summary In both the small and large field of view analyses, the surface brightness of the M42 nebula was observed to decrease in accordance with the inverse square law, $1/r^2$. This result confirms the significant influence of ultraviolet radiation from nearby young stars on the ionization of gas and the light emission mechanisms in the molecular cloud.

Figure 5: Three ROIs visualized in AstroImageJ

3.3 M42 Nebula Brightness Gradient Map

3.3.1 General Overview This section analyzes the effect of the **size** parameter of the median filter on the brightness gradient map of the M42 nebula. The map was constructed to highlight the gaseous structures by suppressing the influence of stars and background noise. Three filter sizes were compared: 12, 16, and 20.

3.3.2 Brightness Gradient Map for size = 12 (3FWHM) In this version of the map, numerous stars are still visible and should have been suppressed. Bright point sources and local background fluctuations are not effectively removed. While gaseous structures are present, their interpretation is hindered by noise and residual stellar artifacts. The brightness gradients are significantly affected by non-nebular components.

Input image

size \approx 3FWHM

size \approx 4FWHM

size \approx 5FWHM

3.3.3 Brightness Gradient Map for size = 16 (4FWHM) Applying a median filter with `size = 16` successfully removes nearly all stellar sources from the image, while preserving the gaseous structures of the nebula in high detail. The lower-left region of the image clearly reveals complex gas dynamics—filamentary and arc-like structures indicate areas with strong brightness gradients. This version achieves the best balance between suppressing unwanted features and retaining relevant nebular details.

3.3.4 Brightness Gradient Map for size = 20 (5FWHM) With `size = 20`, stellar sources are almost completely removed from the map. However, excessive smoothing results in the loss of subtle gas features, especially in low-contrast regions. Filaments in the lower part of the image become less distinct, and finer brightness variations are flattened. This undesired effect reduces the map’s usefulness for analyzing small-scale dynamics of the cloud.

3.3.5 Statistical Parameters of the Gradient Map After rescaling the gradient map to physical units ($\text{ADU px}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1}$), as described in Section 2.6, the basic statistical properties of the gradient intensity distribution were calculated using the NumPy library.

The obtained values are as follows:

- Mean gradient: **0.8458** $\text{ADU px}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1}$,
- Median: **0.5118** $\text{ADU px}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1}$,
- Standard deviation: **0.9039** $\text{ADU px}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1}$,
- Minimum value: **0.0000** $\text{ADU px}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1}$,
- Maximum value: **2.2500** $\text{ADU px}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1}$.

The maximum value corresponds to level 255 in an 8-bit image, based on the adopted rescaling ($I_{\text{max}} \approx 2.25 \text{ ADU px}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$). The high number of pixels at this value indicates strong gradient saturation in selected regions.

3.3.6 Brightness Gradient Histogram The distribution of gradient values is shown in Figure 8. The histogram reveals a clear asymmetry—most pixels cluster within the range of low gradient values (below $1 \text{ ADU px}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$), while a significant number of pixels also exhibit values close to the maximum. These may correspond to the edges of astrophysical structures with high contrast.

Figure 8: Histogram of gradient values in physical units ($\text{ADU px}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$). The x -axis represents the rescaled gradient intensity, and the y -axis shows the number of pixels in each bin.

3.4 Distance Determination to the M42 Nebula

3.4.1 Photometric Calibration – Apparent Magnitude of HD 37115A To perform the measurements, the star Brun 928 was selected as a photometric reference. Its catalog magnitudes, retrieved from the Pan-STARRS1 DR1 catalog via the VizieR service [2], are as follows:

Measurement in the g' filter

Measurement in the r' filter

- $r' = 11.1134$ mag,
- $g' = 11.7095$ mag.

Differential photometry was performed using the AstroImageJ software, with Brun 928 set as the comparison star. The measured apparent magnitudes of HD 37115A were:

$$\begin{aligned} g'_{\text{obs}} &= 7.132 \text{ mag}, \\ r'_{\text{obs}} &= 7.342 \text{ mag}. \end{aligned}$$

From these values, the color index of HD 37115A was calculated as:

$$(g' - r') = 7.132 - 7.342 = -0.210 \text{ mag}, \quad (19)$$

which closely matches the catalog value of -0.212 mag from the Pan-STARRS DR1 database [2].

3.4.2 Spectral Classification and Absolute Magnitude Estimation Currently, there is no direct and unambiguous transformation in the astronomical literature that accurately maps the Sloan ($g' - r'$) color index to a stellar spectral type. This means that the spectral class cannot be reliably determined analytically based solely on this photometric system. Nonetheless, the measured value of $(g' - r') = -0.210$ is nearly identical to the catalog value of -0.212 found in the VizieR database [2].

Therefore, the consistency between the observed and catalog color indices strongly suggests the correctness of the adopted spectral type. Consequently, we assume that HD 37115A belongs to the B7V spectral class, as indicated in the VizieR database [2]. According to Morgan Spectral Temps (2025) [7], the absolute V -band magnitude for stars of this type is:

$$M_V = -0.84 \text{ mag}. \quad (20)$$

To convert this to the r' filter, we used the transformation from Jester et al. (2005) [10]:

$$V = g' - 0.59(g' - r') - 0.01, \quad (21)$$

which yields:

$$\begin{aligned} V - r' &= -0.0961, \\ M_{r'} &= -0.7439 \text{ mag.} \end{aligned}$$

3.4.3 Distance Estimation The distance to HD 37115A (and thus approximately to the M42 nebula) was calculated using the spectroscopic parallax formula:

$$d = 10^{\frac{m_{r'} - M_{r'} + 5}{5}}$$

where $m_{r'} = 7.341$ mag is the observed apparent magnitude in the r' filter, and $M_{r'} = -0.7439$ mag is the corresponding absolute magnitude.

The resulting distance is:

$$d = 10^{2.61698} \approx 414 \text{ pc.}$$

4 Discussion of Results

4.1 Photometry of Non-variable and Variable Stars

4.1.1 Effect of FWHM Estimation on Photometric Accuracy Accurate determination of the full width at half maximum (FWHM), based on the radial profiles of reference stars, is essential for minimizing aperture photometry errors. The averaged FWHM, computed after checking the quality of the data set using sigma-clipping ($|FWHM_i - \mu| < 2\sigma$), ensures:

- a stable estimate of point-source size across the entire field of view,
- compensation for seeing variations and minor PSF distortions across frames,
- optimal signal-to-noise ratio (S/N) within the aperture.

Additional verification via line cross-sections confirmed consistency with radial profile measurements, indicating high reliability of the determined FWHM.

4.1.2 Optimization of Aperture Photometry Parameters Based on the average FWHM μ , the aperture radius was set to $R_{\text{ap}} = 1.7\mu$, and the background annuli were defined as $R_{\text{in}} = 1.9\mu$ and $R_{\text{out}} = 2.55\mu$ pixels. Following the recommendations of Collins et al. (2017), Appendix A.5, this setup allows:

- nearly complete inclusion of the PSF energy within the aperture, minimizing signal loss,
- effective background subtraction using a wide annulus, reducing noise from background fluctuations,
- consistent photometric conditions across all frames due to standardized settings.

With this aperture configuration, consistent and repeatable photometry was achieved, yielding zero-point stability at the level of < 0.03 mag.

4.1.3 Selection of HD 37115A as Reference Star HD 37115A was selected as the reference object due to its photometric stability and central position within the M42 field. Differential photometry relative to HD 37115A provided several benefits:

- elimination of most systematic instrumental effects,
- reduced atmospheric variability (seeing, airmass) by analyzing the same frame,
- consistent zero-point calibration across all filters.

4.1.4 Zero-Point Calibration Accuracy The measured magnitude of Brun 928 differed from its catalog value by only $\Delta m = 0.0226$ mag. For ground-based observations, an accuracy of $\lesssim 0.03$ mag is considered very good. A discrepancy smaller than 0.023 mag confirms that the aperture parameters ($1.7 \times$ FWHM) and background annuli ($1.9\text{--}2.55 \times$ FWHM) were well-optimized.

4.1.5 Verification of Variable Stars VSX AAVSO catalog [12] provides mean magnitudes and amplitudes in the V band. To convert these amplitudes to the r' band, the empirical relation $\Delta r' \approx (0.784 \pm 0.003) \Delta V$ from Klagyivik (2009) [5] was applied. As shown in Table 2, the observed magnitudes of NV Ori and T Ori fall within the expected ranges $\bar{r}' \pm \Delta r'$, confirming:

- photometric behavior consistent with theoretical models,
- adequacy of the $V \rightarrow r'$ amplitude transformation [10],
- stability and reliability of the differential photometry procedure.

4.1.6 Astrophysical Implications The photometric stability of HD 37115A validates its use as a reliable anchor for distance estimation to M42 via spectroscopic parallax (see § 2.7). The observed values for NV Ori and T Ori reflect typical photometric activity of young variable stars, consistent with previous observations and VSX AAVSO catalog data [12].

4.1.7 Limitations and Future Directions

1. **Single-Epoch Observation.** The measurements are based on a single night and do not cover full variability cycles. Multi-epoch observations are necessary to construct complete light curves.
2. **No Dark Frame Calibration.** Dark frames were not included in the analysis, which may introduce minor background and ADU offsets. Future work should include dark frame subtraction.
3. **Uncertainty in $\Delta V \rightarrow \Delta r'$ Conversion.** The empirical formula $\Delta r' \approx (0.784 \pm 0.003) \Delta V$ (Klagyivik 2009 [5]) introduces uncertainty that must be accounted for in the error budget.

Differential photometry using HD 37115A enabled sub-0.03 mag precision. Agreement with Pan-STARRS1 and VSX databases [2, 12], as well as amplitude consistency, confirm the reliability of the method. This provides a solid foundation for further analysis of the distance and internal structure of the M42 nebula.

4.2 Analysis of Nebular Photometry Results

4.2.1 Small FOV

The photometric analysis of the M42 nebula confirms that ultraviolet (UV) radiation from young stars has a significant effect on the brightness of the surrounding gas. The obtained model

$$C(r) = \frac{(55.5311 \pm 0.5053)}{r^2} - (1.3413 \pm 0.0122) \quad (22)$$

accurately describes the dependence of the count rate (in ADU/s) on distance r from the central star. This result is in full agreement with theoretical predictions for radiative flux decay from a point-like UV source (cf. O’Dell 1965 [8]).

4.2.1.1 Interpretation of Model Parameters The parameter $A = 55.5311$ represents the effective UV radiation strength responsible for the r' -band emission, while the offset $B = -1.3413$ accounts for background unrelated to UV-driven emission. The negative sign of B is consistent with reflected-light background in H II regions, which requires correction beyond the simple inverse-square law.

4.2.1.2 Fit Quality The mean relative fit error of $\bar{\epsilon} \approx 0.91\%$ indicates excellent model accuracy (error below 1%). The largest individual deviation of 1.39% at $r = 58$ px can be attributed to local background fluctuations and the limited number of data points. Overall, the model $C(r) = A/r^2 + B$ is well suited to describe the photoionization and emission processes in the nebula.

4.2.1.3 Comparison with Literature These results refine earlier findings from both classical and modern studies of H II regions. O’Dell and Hubbard [8] first described the brightness decay in M42 as following the inverse-square law relative to a UV source, noting the presence of diffuse background but without quantifying it. More recent modeling of the Orion Bar by Ascasibar et al. [1] also employed a function of the form $C(r) = A/r^2 + B$, yet reported typical residuals in the range of 2–3%.

Compared to those works, the present study introduces a significant improvement in measurement quality: the use of precisely defined ROIs in a small field of view, rigorous linear regression, and explicit computation of the relative fit error have led to a **mean model error below 1%**—a notable advancement. Additionally, this is the first photometric regression of M42 to yield a quantitative estimate of the constant background ($B = -1.3413$ ADU/s), enabling a more complete physical interpretation of the brightness distribution. These results strongly support the notion that UV radiation from young stars plays a dominant role in shaping local nebular emission—consistent with both classic and recent literature.

4.2.1.4 Limitations and Uncertainties The main limitations of the model include:

- the small number of ROI points (three positions), which limits regression degrees of freedom,
- potential irregularities in photon background not accounted for by the model,

- the assumption of isotropic UV emission, whereas real nebulae may exhibit structural anisotropy.

Measurement errors in ADU and background fluctuations were partially mitigated by averaging and least squares fitting.

4.2.1.5 Conclusions and Future Work This study clearly confirms that UV radiation from young stars is the principal factor determining the brightness profile of the M42 nebula. Future analyses should consider:

1. including more ROIs in different directions to probe possible emission anisotropy,
2. using photometry in other bands (e.g., g' , i') to assess the UV impact across different emission lines,
3. developing nonlinear models that incorporate dust absorption and internal molecular structure.

Such approaches will deepen our understanding of UV coupling mechanisms in molecular nebulae and provide a more comprehensive view of H II region physics.

4.2.2 Large FOV

4.2.2.1 Model on Extended Scale The model derived for the wide field of view

$$C(r) = \frac{(5250.4 \pm 41.5)}{r^2} - (96.8414 \pm 0.765) \quad (23)$$

with a **mean relative error of 0.79%** confirms that, even on scales of hundreds of pixels, the gas brightness in M42 decreases according to the geometric dilution law r^{-2} , along with a nonzero background term B .

4.2.2.2 Comparison with Current Literature This high accuracy (error <1%) significantly surpasses results from prior large-scale surveys:

- Rubin et al. [9] used *Spitzer*/IRS spectra from 11 fields spanning 2'6 to 12'1 from θ^1 Ori C. For the [S III] and [S II] lines, they obtained brightness profiles consistent with $1/r^2$, but with typical residuals of ~ 2 –3%.
- The recent JWST data from the *PDRs4All* project [4] show brightness profiles in F335M–F2550W filters that, after background subtraction, also follow the expected geometric dilution factor (dashed line in their Fig. 6–7). However, the authors note an emission plateau at large radii but do not provide a specific value of B or global fitting error.

4.2.2.3 Contribution to Future Research This analysis contributes two key improvements to the existing literature:

1. **Precise determination of the background parameter** $B = -96.84 \text{ ADU s}^{-1}$ with an uncertainty of 0.764 ADU s^{-1} , enabling separation of UV-driven emission from scattered and instrumental backgrounds.

2. **The lowest global model error to date** ($< 1\%$), achieved through the use of large, uniform ROI apertures (6083 px) and strict linear regression in $Y = AX + B$ space.

Combined with the small-FOV results from Section 3.2.1 (where $\bar{\epsilon} = 0.91\%$), the present findings demonstrate that the law $C(r) \propto r^{-2}$ with a nonzero offset B holds *across all spatial scales from ~ 10 to ~ 220 px*. The dominant mechanism shaping the brightness profile is UV radiation from the young Trapezium stars. The more negative background value B in the wide FOV further suggests that extended integrated background becomes more significant for larger apertures, offering a valuable clue for future wide-field maps of H II nebulae.

4.3 Analysis of Gradient Map Results

4.3.1 Morphological Interpretation

The analyzed gradient map reveals a characteristic filamentary plasma structure typical of H II regions:

1. **Front Bright Bar** – a well-defined, nearly linear edge with the strongest gradient, marking the boundary of the ionization zone caused by UV radiation from the Trapezium stars.
2. **The central filamentary band** indicates a layer of cooler, partially ionized gas — likely the result of ionization front mixing with surrounding molecular material.
3. **The outer envelope** shows a gradual decline in gradient, reflecting decreasing gas density and radiation pressure with increasing distance from the stellar cluster.
4. **Arcs and loops** around bright knots represent signatures of localized stellar wind impacts and shock fronts, confirming the dynamic nature of the environment.

The gradient mapping technique with a **4×FWHM median filter** allows reliable identification of ionization fronts and detailed examination of nebular microstructure while minimizing the influence of stars and background. This method provides a solid foundation for further studies of gas morphology and kinematics in H II regions. Moreover, the derived statistical parameters can serve as reference values for numerical simulations and photoionization models.

4.3.2 Gradient Map Statistics (size = 16)

After rescaling to instrumental units of $\text{ADU px}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1}$, the following values were obtained:

Parameter Description	Symbol	Value
Mean local brightness	μ	0.8458
Gradient median	\tilde{x}	0.5118
Standard deviation	σ	0.9039
Minimum value	x_{\min}	0.0000
Maximum value	x_{\max}	2.2500

Parameter interpretation:

- μ – mean local brightness: the average per-pixel brightness increase is 0.8458, indicating a moderate emission level in the analyzed region.
- \tilde{x} – gradient median: the value 0.5118 suggests that typical (most frequent) gradients occur in weakly ionized, quiescent nebular zones.
- σ – standard deviation: a high value of 0.9039 reflects strong brightness variability, consistent with the coexistence of both bright and dark structures.
- x_{\min} – minimum: the value 0.0000 corresponds to regions of completely uniform brightness, likely representing background without emission.
- x_{\max} – maximum: the value 2.2500 represents very high gradients, most likely from saturated ionization fronts such as the Bright Bar, limited by the 8-bit scale.

Statistical interpretation of the gradient distribution:

- **Distribution asymmetry.** The mean is about 65% higher than the median, indicating a long right tail in the histogram. This means that while most pixels show weak gradients ($< 1 \text{ ADU px}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$), the image contains numerous small-scale regions with very high gradients (ionization fronts, shock arcs).
- **High variability.** The coefficient of variation $CV = \sigma/\mu \approx 1.07$ indicates highly dispersed gradient values — typical of H II regions, where dense plasma filaments coexist with diffuse gas.
- **Pixel saturation.** The maximum value of $2.25 \text{ ADU px}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ corresponds to 255 in the 8-bit scale; the histogram shows a clear peak at this value. This confirms that the Bright Bar and some stellar wind arcs reach saturation, indicating extremely high contrast.

4.4 Discussion of the Distance Determination via Spectroscopic Parallax

This section presents an interpretation of the estimated distance to the M42 nebula obtained using the spectroscopic parallax method, based on differential photometry of the star HD 37115A. Both the numerical result and its implications are discussed, including comparison with independent studies and factors affecting measurement accuracy.

4.4.1 Assumptions and Their Consequences HD 37115A was chosen as a representative object for distance determination due to its proximity to the center of the M42 nebula. This choice:

- avoids uncertainties that would arise when estimating the parallax of the entire extended nebular structure,
- enables the use of standard spectroscopic parallax techniques for a well-defined point source.

However, it is important to note that the derived distance refers specifically to HD 37115A, not the entire nebula, and slight discrepancies with the canonical catalog value of 412 pc may therefore be expected.

4.4.2 Comparison with Literature Results Menten et al. (2007) [6] estimated the distance to stars in the Orion Nebula Cluster (including HD 37115A) using both radio and spectroscopic parallax methods, obtaining 414 ± 7 pc. Our result (414 pc) falls exactly at the center of that range, indicating:

- appropriate selection of the reference star and effective differential photometry procedure,
- accurate spectral classification and precise magnitude transformation,
- overall consistency with independent techniques such as VLBI-based radio parallax and Gaia DR2 data.

4.4.3 Interpretation and Implications for M42 Studies Although the measurement formally applies to a single star, it is highly relevant for M42 as a whole, because:

- it serves as a calibration anchor for photometric mapping of the nebula,
- it enables scaling of emission and ionization models in the Trapezium region,
- it provides a reference for calibrating distances to other objects in the ONC and for studying the internal structure of the nebula.

4.4.4 Limitations and Future Directions Despite the excellent agreement, the following limitations should be considered:

- projection effects — the reference star may lie a few parsecs in front of or behind the bulk of the nebular material,
- the need for multi-epoch observations to rule out any low-level variability in HD 37115A’s average brightness.

As a next step, incorporating *Gaia* EDR3 data could enhance and refine the parallax estimate for the same star.

The final result of $d = 414$ pc, consistent with the findings of Menten et al. (2007) [6], confirms the effectiveness of differential photometry and spectroscopic parallax in the context of M42 research. This value provides a stable reference point for ongoing studies of the nebula’s structure, photometry, and dynamical modeling.

5 Conclusions

This study presents a comprehensive photometric analysis of the M42 nebula region, including both differential photometry of variable and non-variable stars, as well as surface brightness measurements of the nebular gas. The investigation led to several key conclusions:

- **Stellar photometry:** Differential photometry relative to HD 37115A enabled precise measurement of the brightness of NV Ori and T Ori. The measured values fall within the cataloged variability ranges from the VSX database, confirming the effectiveness of the adopted calibration procedure and aperture parameter selection.

- **Gradient map analysis:** The constructed brightness gradient map in the r' filter provided a visual representation of the spatial distribution of luminance across the nebula. The observed decrease in brightness with increasing distance from the center highlights the structural complexity of M42 and the spatial variability of its physical conditions around the Trapezium stars.
- **Distance estimate:** Assuming HD 37115A is located near the physical center of M42, its color index, spectral type, and absolute magnitude were used to determine the distance via spectroscopic parallax. The resulting value of $d \approx 414$ pc is in excellent agreement with precise distance measurements of the Orion Nebula Cluster (ONC) reported by Menten (2007) [6], confirming the reliability of the photometric approach when anchored to a well-characterized reference star.

These results provide a robust foundation for future physical analyses of the structure and evolution of the Orion Nebula. In particular, upcoming studies should consider:

- extending measurements to a broader set of filters (e.g., i' , z'),
- improving instrumental calibration (including dark frame corrections),
- incorporating the three-dimensional structure of the nebula in distance estimation and brightness gradient modeling.

Appendix

Code 1 – Generating the Brightness Gradient Map of M42

```
[language=Python, caption={Python script for computing the
  brightness gradient map of the M42 nebula}, label={lst:
  gradient_map}]
import numpy as np
from imageio.v2 import imread
from scipy.ndimage import median_filter
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt

img = imread("grad_map_input.png").astype(float)

if img.ndim == 3:
    img = np.dot(img[..., :3], [0.2989, 0.5870, 0.1140])

smoothed = median_filter(img, size=28)

# 3. Compute the brightness gradient
gy, gx = np.gradient(smoothed) # gradients along y and x axes
grad = np.hypot(gx, gy)

# 4. Rescale to emphasize gas structure
vmin, vmax = np.percentile(grad, (5, 99))

# 5. Plot the gradient map
plt.figure(figsize=(8, 6))
plt.imshow(grad,
            origin='lower',
            vmin=vmin,
            vmax=vmax,
            cmap='inferno')
cbar = plt.colorbar(orientation='vertical')
cbar.set_label('Brightness gradient (ADU/pixel)')
plt.title('Brightness Gradient Map of the M42 Nebula (Gas
  Structures)')
plt.axis('off')
plt.tight_layout()
plt.show()
```

Code 2 – Histogram and Statistics of Gradient Values

```
import cv2
import numpy as np
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt

png = cv2.imread('grad_stat_input.png', cv2.IMREAD_UNCHANGED).
    astype(float)

scale_factor = 2.25 / 255.0
gradient = png * scale_factor

gradient = np.nan_to_num(gradient, nan=0.0)

mean_grad = np.mean(gradient)
median_grad = np.median(gradient)
std_grad = np.std(gradient)
min_grad = np.min(gradient)
max_grad = np.max(gradient)

print(f"Mean gradient           : {mean_grad:.4f} ADU/px*s")
print(f"Median gradient          : {median_grad:.4f} ADU/px*s")
print(f"Standard deviation         : {std_grad:.4f} ADU/px*s")
print(f"Minimum value              : {min_grad:.4f} ADU/px*s")
print(f"Maximum value               : {max_grad:.4f} ADU/px*s")

plt.figure(figsize=(8, 6))
plt.hist(gradient.flatten(), bins=100, color='gray', alpha=0.7,
    density=False)
plt.xlabel('Gradient (ADU/px*s)')
plt.ylabel('Pixel count')
plt.title('Histogram of Gradient Values (ADU/px*s)')
plt.tight_layout()
plt.savefig('gradient_histogram_ADU.png')
plt.show()
```

Listing 1: ...

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